

Improving Women's Clothing For Law Enforcement Agencies

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Abstract: *The article suggests that the design of clothing intended for law enforcement agencies is a difficult task, the solution of which includes increasing requirements for the performance characteristics of the clothing being produced, as well as information on the specifics of the professional activity of potential consumers.*

Keywords — Innovative Way technologies, Membrane Materials, Clothing Production, "Smart Textiles", Special Clothing.

INTRODUCTION.

President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev's decision PQ-2800 of February 27, 2017 "on measures to regulate the mechanism of development, standardization, approval and preparation of uniform clothing of ministries, departments and organizations of the Republic of Uzbekistan".[1] the comprehensive reforms carried out in the field of our Republic are instrumental in further raising the prestige of our National Army, establishing its activities in the spirit of the Times, social support of military personnel. These aspects also find a vivid expression in practical efforts to create a new model of military uniform for female servicemen.

The comprehensive reforms carried out in the military sphere in our republic are instrumental in further raising the prestige of our National Army, establishing its activities in the spirit of the Times, social support of military personnel. These aspects also find a vivid expression in practical efforts to create a new model of military uniform for military personnel. [1]

With the participation of designers, psychologists, dress constructors, technologists, scientists and military personnel with vast experience in this direction and Soha personnel qualified for such a comprehensive and extremely responsible task, extensive work is being carried out. All proposals and considerations and recommendations in this direction are implemented by experts with a thorough, comprehensive analysis.

According to industry experts, until this time, the process of preparing military clothing-head climate, environment, season-by-season separation in accordance with natural conditions, specificity of military activity, headdress, shoes, additional tools-did not meet modern requirements. However, in most countries of the world, leading military structures and organizations, there is a practice of a comprehensive, systematic and comprehensive approach to the preparation of military uniforms, involving thousands of scientists, specialists, experts.

According to the analysis, the non-compliance of the fabrics and materials used in the preparation of military uniforms with regulatory requirements, the use of attachments in the dimensions of the uniform of the military, taking into account ergonomic indicators, the provision of uniforms of

military personnel, some shortcomings were observed in the collection of military wardrobe, objectionable cases have been found that the pre-sewn dress was not necessarily scientifically approached in the models and, as a result, various inconveniences were being corrected in the performance of everyday and combat actions by military personnel.[2]

Taking into account all the feedback and recommendations noted above and the shortcomings, preliminary sketches and designs of the uniforms of military personnel and industry personnel were developed. Primary samples of the created uniforms are intended to be tested (aprobated) by the first troops in military units, summarizing in-depth study, analysis, suggestions and comments on the opinion of representatives of the field, military personnel, youth, people, the general public, after which the production of military uniforms in a wide range is established.[4]

It is known that military uniforms-taking into account the fact that the head is composed of such categories as ceremonial, everyday (except for the ranks and ranks), workshop-office, Field Training-Training, special. Systematic, comprehensive work is being carried out taking into account precisely these in the preparation of the design and sketches of the head of clothing for military personnel and industry personnel. In this, Signs, images, all-all strictly taken into account, which distinguish the fabric for the military uniform-head, distinguishing marks (attributes), even the quality of small details, durability, compactness, as well as the category of military personnel and industry personnel.[5]

As a conclusion, we must say that, taking into account geopolitical situations around the world, it is necessary to distinguish military uniforms by season in accordance with climate, environment, natural conditions, to produce military uniforms in accordance with the requirements of the time, considering the specificity of military activity, the process of making hats, shoes, additional tools as a requirement of the current period.[6]

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